

EFFECT OF PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ON SEED COTTON YIELDS AND FIBRE TRAITS

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ABSTRACT

Plant growth regulators are used in cotton production to establish a balance between vegetative and reproductive progression to enhance seed cotton yield and lint quality. The study was conducted at the Cotton Research Station, Vehari in Pakistan, April 2013, with some specific doses of PGRs to observe their effects on yield and yield components of cotton using cultivar 'VH-282'. Three commercial PGRs (cytokinins, auxins and gibberellins) were sprayed with a dose of 20ppm/20liter water at flowering and boll formation stage during the study. The results revealed that the applied PGRs had substantial positive effects on the seed cotton yield, boll retention, boll weight, fiber fineness and CLCuV percentage. However, ginning out turn percentage and fiber length were not affected considerably by the PGR. Higher yields were obtained in Cytokinins treated plots. As a result, PGRs pondered a component of cotton growth management to bring higher seed cotton yields by reducing CLCuV incidence.

Keywords: Plant Growth Regulators, Exogenous hormones, Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.), Cotton Leaf Curl Virus (CLCuV), Fiber Parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Gossypium hirsutum L. being a cash crop play an important role in improving and stabilizing the country economy by providing raw material to the textile industry such as cotton lint as an export item. Pakistan exported textile products worth \$13.1billion which is 53% of total export. During 2012-13, cotton was grown on an area of 2879 thousand hectares with total production of 13 million bales, making an average cotton yield of 769 kg ha^{-1} (Anonymous, 2013). The cotton plant is a perennial with an indeterminate growth habit, and responds to any agitations in its environment with a dynamic growth response that is often unpredictable (Reddy *et al.*, 1997; Zhao *et al.*, 2005). Noticeably, the best means to achieve these aims is through the use of desirable germplasm in the form of well-adapted high-yielding varieties. Conversely, due to assorted environment (e.g., insect, pest, soil, temperature, and rainfall) for cotton, it is virtually impossible to have a perfectly adapted variety capable of providing high produces in all conditions. Therefore, growth regulators and other stress management practices have been used in an effort to securely achieve high yields (Kerby *et al.*, 1993).

Plant hormones are not nutrients, but chemicals in small amounts promotes and influence the growth and development of the plants (Opik *et al.*, 2005). In recent years, synthetic growth regulators have been explored for their capability to alter the cotton growth and development to improve productivity (Güllüoğlu, 2006). PGRs should be considered as management tools in the producer arsenal that can be used to ensure efficient crop production. These composites are diverse in both of their chemistry and use. A comprehensive review of the use of PGRs in cotton

production has been presented by Cothren and Oosterhuis (2000). The aim of this investigation was to study the response of upland cotton cultivars "VH-282" to foliar application with cytokinins, auxins and gibberellic acid as compared with untreated plant regarding seed cotton yield and yield associated components.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in the Research area of Cotton Research Station, Vehari during cotton season April, 2013. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) and replicated thrice. The net plot size was 18.3m x 3m. The concentration of three experimental treatments (auxins, gibberellic acids and cytokinins) was 20ppm per 20 liters H₂O applied to a cotton variety VH-282 while in control no PGR was applied. Seed bed was managed by cultivating soil for 3 times with cultivator each followed by planking. Crop was seeded on the seed bed with sandy clay loam soil. However, nine times of irrigations were practiced and 600ml per acre "Dual Gold" weedicide sprayed as pre- emergence and 2 manual and one tractor hoeing was done. Six pesticides were sprayed against sucking and two were sprayed against boll worm. At each plot, 20 plants were selected and marked to collect data. Total number of bolls, average boll weight and seed cotton picked from 20 nominated plants were weighed in grams using a digital electric balance. Then yield of seed cotton per plant was calculated. GOT percentage was calculated by formula given by Singh (2004).

Ginning Out Turn (%) =

(Total weight of lint in sample/ Total weight of seed cotton yield in that sample) x 100

Fiber characteristics like fiber fineness, fiber strength and fiber length were measured by using HVI-900. Data gathered from different parameters were statistically studied by using MSTAT-C program (Anonymous, 1986) and means were compared using LSD test at 5% probability level (Steel *et al.*, 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results revealed that different growth and yield parameters of cotton were significantly increased in response to the application of various PGRs.

Seed cotton yield (Kgha⁻¹):

By the application of cytokinins, auxins and gibberellic acid average seed cotton yield varied in 3154.3, 2586.3 and 2167.7 kg, respectively as compared with control (1973.3 kg). Data relating to seed cotton yield was distinctly varied by plant growth regulators which showed substantial effect on overall seed cotton yield per hectare (Table 2). The maximum average seed cotton yield per hectare (3154.3kg) was observed in cytokinins application, which varied significantly from all other growth regulator treatment, including control while minimum (1973.3 kg) yield was noted in control (Figure 1). These results are supported by Copur *et al.*, (2010); Hussain *et al.*, (2011) and Majid *et al.*, (2013) who reported that exogenous application of PGR significantly enhanced the seed cotton yield.

Average Boll weight (g):

It is one of the major component of seed cotton yield in upland cotton (Poehlman, 1987). Data given in the Table 2 indicated that cytokinins, auxins and Gibberellins significantly influenced boll weight. Maximum boll weight (3.9 g) was recorded where cytokinin was applied, which was 44.4% higher than the control (Figure 2). The minimum increase in boll weight (12% higher than the control) was observed in response to Gibberellins application. According to the LSD test, there were statistically significant differences in average boll weight between treatments. This might result from accelerating photosynthetic activity and the increase of dry matter concentration by the plant growth regulator which increases boll formation and average boll weight (Sawan *et al.*, 2006). These outcomes agreed with those of (Yagmur *et al.*, 2014) who found an increase in average boll weight by PGR application.

Boll retention:

Cotton has about 90% of boll retention in the first three weeks of blooming under favorable conditions. Around 35-40% of the square normally produced mature bolls (Landivar and Benedict, 1996). Application of gibberellic acid directly to open flowers bolls increased the boll retention percentage

(Walhood, 1957). Maximum boll retention was observed where cytokinin was applied and it was 57.7% higher than the control. Minimum boll retention (0.16% higher than the control) was observed in response to the gibberellic acid application (Figure 3). Among PGRs, cytokinin, auxin and gibberellin play vital role in regulating developmental processes within plant bodies (Gou *et al.*, 2010; Rastogi *et al.*, 2013)

CLCuV (%):

Cotton varieties were susceptible to cotton leaf curl virus (CLCuV) which ultimately reduced overall seed cotton yield (Mansoor *et al.*, 1993; Rehman *et al.*, 2001). The worldwide infection in cotton by CLCuV occurs during early growth stage as compared to later stage. Due to the stages of crop and intensity of the disease, causes up to 90% cotton yield loss. According to the Table-2, application of growth regulators reduced the viral attack due to better health of plants. Cytokinins application reduced 50.9%, susceptible level followed by auxins (35.2%) and gibberellic acid (26%) as compared to control (Figure 4). According to the LSD test treatments showed significant differences regarding CLCuV incidence.

Ginning out turn (%), Fiber elongation (mm), and Fiber fineness (micronaire):

Data regarding ginning out turn are presented in Table-2. A review of data indicated that PGR did not influence ginning out turn significantly compared with untreated control. However, ginning out turn ranged between 37.9% to 38.5%, among the different treatment of growth regulators (Figure 5). Fiber length was influenced by both genetic and environmental factors (Meredith and Bridge, 1993). In addition, Fiber length is affected partly by cultural practices and the type of PGRs (Siebert and Stewart, 2006). There were no significant differences in Fiber length according to PGRs applications (Figure 6). Similar results were reported by Jost and Dollar (2004) and Gencsoylu (2009).

Fiber fineness is another essential qualitative character, which plays a major part in defining the spinning value of cotton. It was observed that Fiber fineness was not affected by PGR (Copur *et al.*, (2010). But data exhibited that cytokinins, auxins and gibberellic acid considerably affect the fiber fineness by improving lint quality (Figure 7).

CONCLUSIONS

Research into the effects of hormones on cotton yield and fiber development made significant progress in the last few decades. This analysis indicated that application of Plant Growth Regulators considerably

influence the seed cotton yield, boll weight, boll retention, CLCuV % age and fiber fineness. The use of cytokinins, auxins and gibberellic acids improved average seed cotton yield, when compared to control plots. Therefore, these PGRs can be endorsed to cotton producers to increase seed yield. The lint quality containing fiber elongation and GOT % were not influenced by the Plant Growth Regulators. But fiber fineness was improved by their application. However, by changing the quantity of growth regulator and plant phase, results may be different towards fiber traits.

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Table 1: Treatments, Application period and Recommended rates of Plant Growth Regulators.

Treatments	Application Period	Rates
Cytokinins, Auxins, Gibberellins	First Flowering&Boll formation	20ppm per 20 liter of H ₂ O

Table 2: The effect of Plant Growth Regulators on yield, Boll weight, Boll Retention, gining out turn percentage (GOT %), CLCuV %, Staple length and Fiber Fineness are presented in Table-1.

Treatment	Seed cotton yield Kg/ha	Boll Weight (g)	Boll Retention (%)	CLCuV %	GOT %	Staple Length (mm)	Fiber Fineness (micronaire)
Cytokinin	3154.3	3.9	75.667	42.667	38.467	25.2	5.4
Auxin	2586.3	3.4333	63	56.333	38.2	26.667	5.3667
Gibberelic acid	2167.7	3.0667	55	64.333	37.933	27.733	4.5333
Control	1973.3	2.7333	48	87	38.8	27.933	4.5
Grand Mean	2470.4	3.2833	60.417	62.583	38.35	26.883	4.95
LSD (0.05)	475.27	0.3194	10.333	10.312	0.7468	3.005	0.76
CV	9.63	4.87	8.56	8.25	0.97	5.59	7.69

Figure 1

Figure 2

Table 3: Statistical analysis of growth and quality characters of *Gossypim hirsutum* L.

Yield(Kgha ⁻¹)		CLCuV (%)		Avg. Boll Weight		Avg. Boll Retention		GOT (%)		Fiber length		Fiber Fineness	
F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value
14.49	0.0037	38.85	0.0003	29.43	0.0005	15.8	0.003	2.95	0.1203	2.08	0.2043	5.20	0.0417

Source= Replication df= 2, Treatment df=3, Error df=6, total df =11

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 illustrates Effects of Cytokinins, Auxins and gibberellins on Seed Cotton Yield, Boll weight, Boll Retention, CLCuV %, GOT %, Staple Length and Fibre Fineness respectively.